

Melting Behaviour of Some Pure N-Acyl Amino Acids and Peptides

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Fifty three tlc pure N-acyl amino acids were synthesized by Schotten-Baumann reaction from glc pure odd and even chain fatty acids and chromatographically homogeneous amino acids and a few N-acyl peptides were prepared through the carboxylic carbonic anhydride intermediates. The melting points are reported and discussed.

N-ACYL amino acids and peptides are finding use as surfactants and surfactant intermediates¹. The melting points of several even chain fatty acids derivatives were reported by earlier workers²⁻¹⁸ and the m.p.s of only N-acylsarcosines of odd and even chain fatty acids were reported by Jungermann *et al*¹³. Systematic data on the effect of structure of these compounds on their melting behaviour are not available, and hence this investigation. The surfactant properties of the sodium salts of these acids are being communicated separately.

Experimental

Preparation of glc pure fatty acids: GLC pure even chain fatty acids from decanoic to octadecanoic were prepared from commercially available fatty acids by ester fractionation and crystallisation technique². Hendecanoic acid was prepared from laboratory hydrogenated methyl hendecanoate. Tri, penta and heptadecanoic acids were prepared through the nitrile route^{3,4} from even chain fatty alcohols obtained by sodium reduction of the corresponding glc pure fatty acid esters.

Preparation of N-acyl amino acids: Fatty acid chlorides were prepared using thionyl chloride according to the procedure of Bauer⁵ and further purified by vacuum distillation. These were condensed by Schotten-Baumann reaction with chromatographically homogeneous amino acids, viz, glycine (gly), DL-alanine (ala), DL-valine (val), L-leucine (leu), L-aspartic acid (asp) and L-lysine (lys). Pure sarcosine (sar), ϵ -amino caproic acid and ω -amino hendecanoic acid derivatives were also prepared to study the effect of structure on melting behaviour.

In general, appropriate acid chloride was added dropwise, with constant stirring, to an aqueous solution of sodium salt of amino acid (taken in 20% molar excess except for lysines where 3 moles of acid chloride per mole of amino acid was used) while maintaining the temperature at $45 \pm 5^\circ$; the

pH of the reaction mixture being maintained at 10 ± 0.5 by careful addition of 10% aqueous NaOH solution. The stirring was continued at the same temperature for 1 hr more after the addition was over, and the product was acidulated with 30% sulphuric acid. The separated N-acyl amino acid was taken in an appropriate solvent, washed free of mineral acid and repeatedly crystallised from appropriate solvent till completely free from fatty acids as adjudged by tlc.

Toluene was found to be suitable for extraction of N-acyl glycines, -alanines and -lysines, while hexane gave good results for -valines and -leucines; 95% ethanol was found to be good solvent for crystallisation for all these. For the N-acyl sarcosines, ethyl ether was used as extraction solvent and hexane as solvent for purification by crystallisation.

N-acyl aspartates were prepared in aqueous acetone according to Takehara *et al*⁶ instead of plain aqueous media as for others.

Preparation of N-acyl peptides: N-acyl glycol glycines were prepared from 2,5-diketopiperazine⁷ and acid chloride according to Koebner⁸. The others were prepared by an evolved procedure through the carboxylic carbonic anhydrides. The details of preparation of hendecanoyl glycol alanine are as follows.

N-hendecanoyl glycine was taken in tetrahydrofuran, and to it was added triethylamine in 20% molar excess; the contents were cooled to -5° while stirring and ethyl chloroformate (again 20% molar excess) was added drop by drop while maintaining the temperature at 5° . After completion of addition, the mixture was stirred for another 10 min followed by addition of 10% aqueous solution of sodium salt of DL-alanine (20% molar excess). The contents were then allowed to reach room temperature, further stirred for 30 min and acidified to a pH of 3.0. The precipitate formed was washed till free of mineral acid, and the N-hendecanoyl glycol alanine

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TABLE 1—MELTING POINTS OF PURE N-ACYL AMINO ACIDS

No. of atoms C-atoms in parent acid and its m.p. (in brac- kets)	Melting points, °C. (Figures in brackets are earlier reported values)						
	Amino acid						
	Glycine	DL-alanine	Sarcosine	DL-valine	L-leucine	L-aspartic acid	L-lysine
10 (36.5)	113	97	36.5 (37.5-38.5) ^{1a}	90	109 (109-109.5) ^{1a}	103	113
11 (28.0)	114	102	48.5 (49.4-50.2) ^{1a}	80.5	108 (108-109) ^{1a}	—	113
12 (44.1)	117 (117-118) ^{9,10}	104 (95-96) ¹⁷ (103-105) ^{9,10,18}	45.6 (45.2-45.8) ^{1a}	92 (91-92) ¹⁴	107 (106-107) ¹⁴	109 (107-109) ⁶	117
13 (41.6)	118	107	58.6 (59.8-60) ^{1a}	82.6	103	—	—
14 (54.3)	121 (121-122) ⁹	109	52.0 (51-52) ^{1a}	97.0	101	115	119
16 (62.8)	123* (121) ¹⁰	114 (116-117) ⁹ (106) ¹⁰	60.0 (65.5-66.5) ^{1a}	99.0 (95-98.5) ¹⁵	91.0 (88-89) ¹⁶	118	122 (121-122) ¹⁶
17 (61.1)	124	114	71.4 (71.4-71.9) ^{1a}	83.5	87.3	—	—
18 (69.5)	127 (125-127) ¹¹ (123) ¹²	116 (115-117) ¹¹ (108-110) ¹²	71.5 (65.6-66.5) ^{1a} (71.8-72) ^{1a}	100	65.0	119	—

* m.p.s of linear N-acyl amino acids having a total 18 C-atoms are as follows :

Pentadecanoyl-β-alanine, 115° ; dodecanoyl-ε-amino caproic acid, 86° ; heptadecanoyl-11-amino hendecanoic acid, 98°.

was crystallized from tetrahydrofuran repeatedly till a product of constant m.p. was obtained.

N-hendecanoyl alanyl glycine was similarly prepared from N-hendecanoyl alanine and sodium glycinate ; so also N-acyl glycyglycyl glycinates were prepared from N-acyl glycinates with sodium salt of glycyglycyl glycine, and condensation of N-hexadecanoyl glycyglycyl glycine with sodium salt of glycyglycyl glycine gave N-hexadecanoyl glycyglycyl glycyglycyl glycine.

Determination of melting points : All the products were taken in closed capillary and their melting points were determined by the usual method.

Discussion

The determined acid values (not reported here) and also the determined nitrogen content of the peptides agree closely with theoretical values confirming the purity of products as tested by tlc. The m.p.s of thirty N-acyl amino acids are being reported for the first time ; the m.p.s of others are closer to the values reported earlier with a few exceptions (Table 1). The m.p.s reported by Spivack and Kroll¹² for stearic acid derivatives of glycine (123°), alanine (110°) and sarcosine (66.5°) are consistently lower than the present values (127, 116 and 71.5°, respectively). The present values, however, are nearer to the values reported by Fieser *et al.*¹¹ (stearoyl glycine 127° and stearoyl alanine

117°) and Jungermann *et al.*¹³ (stearoyl sarcosine, 72°). Koebner⁸ reported a m.p. of 172° for hexadecanoyl glycyglycyl glycine which is lower than the value (179°) obtained in the present study by 7° ; the m.p.s of the other acyl peptides are being reported for the first time (Table 2).

TABLE 2—MELTING POINTS OF N-ACYL PEPTIDES

Peptide	Melting point, °C	
	Acid	
	Hendecanoic	Hexadecanoic
gly. glycine	182	179*
gly. alanine	168	—
ala. glycine	141	—
gly. gly. glycine	211	208
gly. gly. gly. glycine	—	229

* Reported m. p. is 172° ; soon after melting all the compounds get darkened due to decomposition.

The effect of increasing the acyl chain length on m.p. of homologues varied from series to series. The N-acylated sarcosine series resembles the fatty acid series in alternation of m.p.s of odd and even

chain compounds, but the alternations are opposite. Alternation is apparent (Fig. 1) in valine series also, but here it is like that for fatty acids, i.e. the m.p. of even acyl chain compounds is higher than that of the odd acyl chain compounds having one carbon atom more. If the odd and even acyl chain compounds of valine and sarcosine are treated as separate series, the m.p.s increase as the series are ascended as in the case of fatty acids. Alternation is absent in the series of glycines, alanines, lysines and leucines; in the case of the first three series, m.p.s increase as the series are ascended, but they decrease in the case of N-acyl leucines, indicating that shorter acyl chain derivatives are packed more closely in solid state. This differential melting behaviour of homologues belonging to different series is, no doubt, due to the differences in structure of the amino acid present.

Fig. 1. Relations of No. of C-atoms in the N-acyl amino acids and their melting points. (gly, glycines; asp, aspartates; ala, alanines; val, valines; sar, sarcosines and leu, leucines)

Compared to parent fatty acids, N-acyl amino acids have higher m.p., the exceptions being decanoyl and tetradecanoyl sarcosines and N-octadecanoyl leucine (Table 1). The difference in m.p. of lower and higher homologues for the N-acyl amino acids is not much as compared to that of fatty acids except for sarcosine and leucine series which perhaps can again be attributed to structural differences of amino acids.

DL-alanines (α -methyl glycines) do not show alternation in melting behaviour while the sarcosines (N-methyl glycines) do for any given acyl chain; the compounds in former series have higher m.p. than those of the latter even though their molecular weights are same.

The magnitude of substituent group at the α -position of the glycines also plays an important role in the melting behaviour. For any given acyl chain, alanines (α -methyl glycines) have higher m.p. than valines (α -isopropyl glycines) which in turn melt

at a higher temperature than leucines (α -isobutyl glycines). Further, as has already been mentioned, as the molecular weight is progressively increased, m.p. increases in alanine series, alternates in valine series and decreases in leucine series. Aspartates (decarboxylates) have m.p.s between those of the corresponding glycines and alanines. All these indicate that the substituent group plays an important role on the intramolecular interaction forces exerted by acyl chains, intermediate amido groups and terminal carboxyl groups of the compounds altering the packing of molecules in solid state. Two long acyl chains as in lysines (diacylated lysines) make the compounds behave like the corresponding glycines. Even though the molecular weights of compounds of the former series are nearly twice of the corresponding ones in the latter, their m.p.s are very close and in two cases they coincide (Table 1). That the position of the intermediate amido group also has a significant effect on the molecular packing in solid state is clear from a comparison of the melting points of four linear N-acyl amino acids having a molecular weight of 313 (having a total of 18 carbon atoms). N-hexadecanoyl glycine (m.p. 123°) has higher m.p. than N-pentadecanoyl alanine (m.p. 115°) which in turn melts higher than N-heptanoyl amino hendecanoic acid (m.p. 98°). These three compounds have 1, 2 and 10 methylene groups between the terminal carboxyl group and nitrogen atom. This indicates that m.p. decreases as the amido group moves away from the carboxyl group in the molecule but again increases when it is nearer to the other end of the molecule (N-dodecanoyl-amino caproic acid melts at 86°).

Incorporating glycine groups increases the m.p. The m.p. of N-hexadecanoyl glycine (123°) is almost twice that of palmitic acid (62.8°). Presence of additional amido groups in the former increases the m.p. further but not linearly (m.p.s of N-hexadecanoyl glyceryl glycine, -glyceryl glyceryl glycine, -glyceryl glyceryl glycine are 179, 208 and 229°, respectively). Here also, like the leucines and unlike other acyl amino acid series, the hendecanoyl derivatives have higher m.p. than those of their corresponding higher homologues (hexadecanoyl derivatives) indicating the combined effect of acyl chain length and the polar part of the molecule on the melting behaviour.

In the peptides also, presence of substituted group (methyl) decreases the m.p. (Table 2); N-hendecanoyl glyceryl glycine melts at a temperature (m.p. 182°) higher than that for hendecanoyl glyceryl alanine (m.p. 168°) and hendecanoyl alanyl glycine (m.p. 141°). It is interesting to note that the sequence of amino acids in peptides has a profound effect on the molecular packing.

The length of the acyl chain as well as the structure of amino acid present in the compounds play an important role in the melting behaviour and in addition to these, the number and sequence of amino acids present have a profound effect on the molecular packing of N-acyl peptides.

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